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A Centralized Network Management Application for Academia and Small Business Networks

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ABSTRACT

Software-defined networking (SDN) is reshaping the networking paradigm. Previous research shows that SDN has advantages over traditional networks because it separates the control and data plane, leading to greater flexibility through network automation and programmability. Small business and academia networks require flexibility, like service provider networks, to scale, deploy, and self-heal network infrastructure that comprises of cloud operating systems, virtual machines, containers, vendor networking equipment, and virtual network functions (VNFs); however, as SDN evolves in industry, there has been limited research to develop an SDN architecture to fulfil the requirements of small business and academia networks. This research proposes a network architecture that can abstract, orchestrate, and scale configurations based on academia and small business network requirements. Our results show that the proposed architecture provides enhanced network management and operations when combined with the network orchestration application (NetO-App) developed in this research. The NetO-App orchestrates network policies, automates configuration changes, secures container infrastructure, and manages internal and external communication between the campus networking infrastructure.

KEYWORDS

Ansible, Automation, Clair, Flask, Kubernetes, Magnum, Network Management System, Network Programmability, NetO-App, OpenStack, OpenContrail, OpenFlow, Orchestration, Python, SDN

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The D-basis Algorithm for Association Rules of High Confidence

Oren Segal, Justin Cabot-Miller, Kira Adaricheva and J.B.Nation

ABSTRACT

We develop a new approach for distributed computing of the association rules of high confidence on the attributes/columns of a binary table. It is derived from the D-basis algorithm developed by K.Adaricheva and J.B.Nation (Theoretical Computer Science, 2017), which runs multiple times on sub-tables of a given binary table, obtained by removing one or more rows. The sets of rules retrieved at these runs are then aggregated. This allows us to obtain a basis of association rules of high confidence, which can be used for ranking all attributes of the table with respect to a given fixed attribute. This paper focuses on some algorithmic details and the technical implementation of the new algorithm. Results are given for tests performed on random, synthetic and real data.

KEYWORDS

Binary table, association rules, implications, the Dbasis algorithm, parallel computing, the relevance.

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Key Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction of Non-Tenured IT Faculty in the USA

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ABSTRACT

This study increased the overall knowledge of job satisfaction among non-tenured IT faculty by way of contributing to the body of management knowledge in the IT environment. The study results provided higher education institution IT leaders and management the vision and understanding to handle job satisfaction issues within the IT environment. This information is also crucial in helping higher education institutions perform at high levels of employee retention, flexibility, and employee job satisfaction by focusing on autonomy and the opportunity for advancement. This quantitative research examined the relationship between (a) the extrinsic motivators (predictor/independent variables), operationalized as autonomy; (b) the intrinsic motivators, operationalized as advancement opportunities; and (c) the job satisfaction level of IT faculty in higher educational institutions (dependent variable). This research has added to the body of knowledge regarding what is needed for IT educators to have job satisfaction by examining how much the independent variables affect job satisfaction of IT faculty in higher educational institutions. We have defined and analyzed methods and practices that companies could apply as they formulate the essential skills and resources for predicting job satisfaction among IT faculty. In this area of job satisfaction, additional understanding could support higher education institutions learning how to keep experienced IT faculty. To examine the extent to which autonomy and opportunity for advancement predict job satisfaction, a multiple linear regression was conducted. This study added to the existing body of knowledge regarding what is needed for IT educators to have job satisfaction by examining how much the independent variables of opportunity for advancement and autonomy affect job satisfaction of IT faculty in higher educational institutions. Additional knowledge in this area of job satisfaction may support higher educational institutions in learning how to retain experienced IT faculty. By addressing these factors related to job satisfaction, employers can better understand what motivates and keeps IT workers satisfied in their jobs. Keeping IT employees satisfied will help retain them and prevent them from job-hopping

KEYWORDS

USA IT Faculty, IT Job Satisfaction, IT Professionals in Education, Non-tenured Position, Higher Educational Institute, IT Faculty Motivation, IT Job in Academia

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